

Enhancing Educational Board Games with Augmented Reality and Deep Learning

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XÜLASƏ

Təhsil xarakterli ənənəvi oyunlar rəqəmsal oyunlardan fərqli olaraq, həm maliyyə, həm də oyun məlumatlarını əks etdirmək baxımından inkişafını məhdudlaşdırır. Bu işdə “Yasaq” adlı ciddi oyunlardan alınan məlumatlar əsasında Artırılmış Reallıq ilə zənginləşdirilməsi araşdırılıb. Bu oyundan toplanan məlumatlar Dərin Öyrənmə ilə öyrədilərək təsnif edib AR ilə birləşdirildi. Oyundakı sözləri dərin öyrənmə vasitəsilə sinifləndirmə vacibdir çünki oyundakı sözlər bu sinif sahəsində onu daha başa düşülən və ya izah edilə bilən edir. AR vasitəsilə oyunda siniflərin göstərilməsi ənənəvi oyunlara nisbətən daha çox interaktivliyi artırır və müxtəlif ipucu seçimlərinin əlavə edilməsi oyunun gedişatına çox təsir edir. Həmçinin, AR vasitəsilə əlavə edilən siniflər və ya göstərişlər sonradan artırıla, dəyişdirilə və ya silinə bilər. Bu tədqiqat ənənəvi stolüstü oyunlarını təkmilləşdirmək üçün AR və dərin öyrənməni birləşdirərək gələcək təkmilləşdirmələr üçün geniş miqyaslı tətbiq edilə bilən və uyğunlaşa bilən bir yanaşma təqdim edir. Bu cür texnologiyaların tətbiqi ənənəvi oyunların fiziki məhdudiyyətlərini aradan qaldıraraq və oyuna virtual funksiyalar gətirərək o oyunları istifadə etmək və daha çox başa düşməyə kömək edir.

Реферат

Образовательные традиционные игры, в отличие от цифровых игр, могут отражать ограниченный объем информации, что ограничивает как финансовую, так и игровую разработку. В этом исследовании было исследовано обогащение с помощью дополненной реальности на основе данных из серьезных игр под названием «Yasaq». Данные, собранные из этой игры, были обучены и классифицированы с помощью глубокого обучения и объединены с AR. Тегирование с помощью глубокого обучения важно, поскольку слова в игре могут использоваться в этом поле тегов как фактор, помогающий сделать ее более понятной или объяснимой. Отображение тегов в игре с помощью AR увеличит интерактивность по сравнению с традиционными играми, а различные варианты подсказок будут иметь большее влияние в ходе игры. Кроме того, теги или подсказки, добавленные с помощью AR, могут быть добавлены, заменены или удалены позже. Это исследование предоставляет масштабируемый и адаптируемый подход для будущих улучшений путем слияния AR и глубокого обучения для создания нового способа улучшения традиционных настольных игр. Применение таких технологий повысит физические пределы традиционных игр и привнесет в игру виртуальные функции, помогая этим играм использоваться и пониматься лучше.

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ABSTRACT

Educational traditional games, unlike digital games, can reflect a limited amount of information, which limits both financial and game development. In this case study, enrichment with Augmented Reality based on the data from the serious games called "Yasaq" was investigated. The data collected from this game was trained and classified with Deep Learning and combined with AR. Tagging via deep learning is important because the words in the game can be used in this tag field as a factor to help make it more understandable or explainable. Showing tags in the game through AR will increase more interactivity than traditional games, and different hint options will have more influence in the course of the game. Also, tags or hints added through AR can be added, replaced or deleted later. This study provides a scalable and adaptable approach for future improvements by merging AR and deep learning to build a fresh way to improve traditional board games. The application of such technologies will raise the physical limits of traditional games and bring virtual functionalities to the game, helping those games to be used and understood more.

Key words: Deep Learning, Augmented Reality, Serious Games, Neural Network, Text Recognition

INTRODUCTION

The integration of AR into educational practices is a very active and bourgeoning area of research. This integration is a growing research area that improves learning experiences in changing technological environments such as Industry 4.0, etc. The integration of deep learning with AR-based serious game has expanded the potential of these technologies to improve education quality. AR is utilized to overlay digital information onto physical board games for creating enriched and interactive learning experiences to users. Google Cloud Vision is employed specifically for its robust and real-time text recognition capabilities. It offers Optical Character Recognition (OCR) for diverse text types which helps to use recognize texts to pass to deep learning classification within AR applications.

Studies have traced the evolution of AR in education over the past 25 years, highlighting its transition from limited, hardware-constrained applications to more accessible, mobile-based platforms (Garzón, 2021). AR has shown significant promise in improving student engagement and comprehension, particularly in STEM fields. For instance, Pasaréti et al. (2018) demonstrated the effectiveness of AR-enhanced materials in secondary school chemistry classes, where students using AR outperformed those using traditional textbooks. The role of AR within the framework of Education 4.0 has also been emphasized. Juhás et al. (2018) talked about the necessity for educational systems to change in tandem with industrial growth. Mostly it is needed by incorporating augmented reality into learning environments. Usage of AR applications in this context provides students with interactive experiences in real-time. Also it combines theoretical knowledge and practical applications into one application with different media types

Researches by Lee (2012) and Bower et al. (2014) has examined AR's application across various educational settings. These findings states that adding visualized objects into that kind of applications makes learning more engaging. Moreover, AR with these kind of changes can enhance various learning environments via making it interactive. It does help more engagement for individual and group activities. Several approaches were researched for working with serious games. Different methods learned for

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working with textual data in such platforms (Mammadli, 2023). Integration of deep learning into AR applications further enhances capabilities of learning methods. Estrada and others. (2022) created a framework to help students learn about electrical engineering laboratory equipment and improve their learning experiences. This framework not only helps in learning the skill, but also improves understanding of complex topics in engineering. Furthermore, Ang and Lim (2019) focused on the creation of interactive and immersive learning experiences while exploring the potential combination Machine Learning (ML) with AR for removing limitations in STEM learning experiences (Mammadli, Ismayilov, 2023).

Despite the promising results, several challenges remain in the widespread adoption of AR and deep learning in education (Wu et al, 2013), including issues related to accessibility, usability, and the integration of these technologies into existing educational frameworks. The future of AR and deep learning in education lies in their ability to seamlessly blend real and virtual environments, creating immersive learning experiences that are both effective and accessible. A number of obstacles remain for application of AR and deep learning in educational context. It is also challenging that integrate these technologies into existing educational frameworks and make it accessible. This framework merges real and virtual environment while keeping effective learning experiences. The future of this framework rests on its ability to combine accessible and effective methods.

METHODS

Our work’s focus is generating hints for players using deep learning with AR. The study uses the database of a serious game called "Yasaq". Our method uses this dataset to demonstrate integration of deep learning and AR for enhancing the learning experience. It provides interactive and updatable content. This approach can significantly improve educational context to create more engaging learning environments.

Data

The "Yasaq" dataset consists of 5,000 cards with six words. Each card contains a main word and five associated taboo words. Players need to describe the main word without using taboo words. These rules boost players' memory by encouraging them to think of creative ways to convey the key word while also remembering related taboo words. However, sometimes it can be difficult to explain the main word. "Yasaq" mechanic is both fun and thought-provoking, which makes it helpful asset to use in schools. Some educational institutions already using such games.

0	PENCIL	PAPER	DRAWER	INK	BAG	BOOK	item
1	CAR	DRIVER	WHEEL	RAIL	ROAD	TRANSPORT	item
2	PHONE	SCREEN	INTERNET	MOBILE	KEY	SMS	item
3	BEAR	YELLOW	HONEY	FURRY	BEE	SLEEP	animal
4	GRADUATE	SCHOOL	STUDY	GRADE	DEGREE	UNIVERSITY	human

Fig 1. Each row represents one card (Main word and 5 taboo words) with a label

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In this database, TF-IDF (Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency) embedding techniques were used to convert text data into vectorized format. A transformed format was needed for machine learning models to understand input values coming from serious game dataset. TF-IDF is an effective embedding method to capture the importance of words in context. It considers both the frequency of a term and its inverse frequency in the entire data set. This presentation allows you to get more accurate results in the "Yasaq" database.

Classification

Multinomial Naïve Bayes (MNB) is a suitable model for classifying datasets like ours. It calculates probability of each category based on word frequency. It provides an ability to perform the classification, using small training sets, not requiring to be continuously re-trained. MNB assumes that words (features) follow a multinomial distribution, which makes it particularly effective for such textual data. It classifies each card into predefined categories given occurrence and distribution of words in the database.

A Multilayer Perceptron (MLP) can also be effectively applied to our embedded dataset by passing them through multiple hidden layers to capture complex relationships between words. Therefore it is effective to classify each card into its respective category. The MLP's structure starts with an input layer corresponding to the number of features (TF-IDF dimensions), then continues with one or more hidden layers to capture nonlinear patterns, and final layer for predicting the category. This structure handles complex connections between main and related words which results in more accurate classification results compared to simpler models.

Augmented Reality

In our approach, for creating AR based application Unity game platform used. Unity platform allows developers to code games once and easily deploy for different platforms. For scripting language C# used in Unity. Also AR plugins in unity give us versatile options to work with. Using the AR plugin, we activate the functionality and put a marker for it to recognize our playing cards. Based on the information in those well-known images, we take the key word with Google Cloud vision and show the label along with the card that we received the answer from deep learning through the API. Application gets real-time information using Google Cloud vision so it can process and get valuable labels to use.

RESULTS

In our approach, deep learning results play the role of hints for users. As dataset "Yasaq" is used for validating analyzed classification methodologies. These tests are to enable the reader to assess the validity of the result. Comparison of methods' results shown on Fig X. Deep learning model with TF-IDF embedding gives more accurate results.

ML and feature extraction methods	Testing accuracy
Multilayer Perceptron + TFIDF	0.96
MultinomialNB + TFIDF	0.92

Fig 2. Results of Deep learning

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The deep learning part is called with API in Unity application which uses Augmented Reality. This AR application recognizes a picture of the traditional version of the game as a card and scans the main word as text and passes it to the API. API returns results from pretrained model and displays them on application.

Fig 3. Displaying in AR

In Fig. 3, you can see the recognition of the card after the installation of the AR and the appearance of the corresponding label on it. It simply gets information from the card and gives hints for users. This application can contain various types of tips, and it is important not only to have text, but also images, videos, gifs, etc. format data can also be added.

DISCUSSION

Integrating augmented reality and deep learning into traditional games helps games evolve and bring even more new functionalities. Normally traditional games are reprinted to make changes on design, mechanic or information. You don't need to go through the reprinting stages with augmented reality based applications. Both materially and flexibly, such applications are preferable to reprinting.

In our approach, the application of deep learning technology with TF-IDF embedding gave quite good results. Multilayer Perceptron can correctly classify almost all cards with a score of 0.96. The answers we received are sufficient for our current game and can be applied to other word games. In the future, it is possible to expand those hints by using different sources and even decorate them with different media on the player's side. However, there are many challenges that need to be overcome before doing so. It is important to have a good base for such word games. Not all traditional games have this kind of database.

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Considering the development of current technology, almost all mobile devices support AR, but there are differences between them.

In conclusion, applying AR and enriching traditional games with deep learning overcomes the limitations of current games, and making the use of such applications available to players will further increase demand. The spread of such games in education, along with their application in many subjects, will increase the learning habits of students and help them remember that teaching in a more fun way.

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